

INNOVATIVE WAYS OF TEACHING SPEECH ACTS THROUGH AUDITORY SKILLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10575350>

Abstract

Listening is one of the most inseparable parts of academic skills and considered to be meaningful not only in receiving information, but also in constructing an interaction between speakers in social and academic situations. As a result, it can be a pivotal tool for bridging pragmatic competences of the learners through the diverse speech acts in various scenarios.

Keywords: speech acts, pragmatics, listening skills, scenarios, simulations, authenticity, receptive and productive skills.

Introduction

Obviously, listening skills are obtained capabilities that entitle a learner's comprehension without using a lot of attempts. On the contrary, listening strategies are the processes which require much effort or challenges and identified as arranged and conscious means that are accepted to enhance perception and negotiation.

In most cases listeners use both skills and strategies to conduct their listening procedures allowing to their interactive goals. This paper aims to demonstrate the practical development of listening skills and proposes some specific tips based on the experience of the teacher: it also depicts some types of assessment which may be utilized in evaluating receptive and productive skills by considering the linguistic and pragmatic aspects of the activities.

There are some specific cases when learners or listeners can move between listening skills and strategies. For example, if you are attending a certain type of seminar or conference your role is not only to be a listener, but also the learner who has to take some notes, here, a note-taking skill is a progressing way of transition from one position to another one or you can actively take part in asking or responding to questions, this is an illustration of passing from passive state to active state by an interaction.

According to J.C. Richards (1983) there are 33 micro skills for communicative listening which can be also interpreted as sub skills of listening.

Simultaneously to this approach another tendency was developed by Vandergrift and Goh (2012), mutually they established six core skills that are important to the listening procedure. By and large, these micro skills and core skills can be similar to each other in some cases. For example, Core skill 2 (Listening selectively can be accomplished due to choosing the most important pieces of listening which unidentified for specific goals) can match micro skill 32 (determines the capability to adjust listening strategies to several types of learners' goals).

One more good illustration can be the appropriate similarity between Core skill 23 (ability to guess results from situations depicted) and Micro skill 6 (Listen and predict –anticipating what is a speaker going to say based on the events).

Undoubtedly, these skills play an integral part for teaching and learning processes; in particular, they can be fruitful in planning, selecting and evaluating stages. They also guide teachers to develop listening processes and tasks by applying them in classrooms or beyond.

It is commonly known that ESOL specialists mostly segregate listening skills into various types, for instance, intensive and extensive types of listening, responsive and autonomous listening, selective and interactive versions of listening, finally, general and academic listening skills.

According to most listening types, it is important to distinguish the message or content of the speech, these types of listening particularly focus on daily negotiations, for example, interaction between two friends, communication among sellers and consumers, while academic listening can be built on academic contexts, such as, IELTS or TOEFL exams are the most significant samples for academic type of listening.

Discussions and assessments

Throughout my teaching experience I have conducted several types of tests for many times. Almost every year at the start of academic season we are asked to organize placement tests for new learners. This type of tests is created in order to arrange the students to the groups. The process of preparing materials for the test is a long lasting procedure which is periodically commenced in the initial month of summer and ended in August. Practically, placement tests are crucial in our teaching as they help segregating learners to the groups and this method has successfully shown its efficacy. Preferably, we utilize multiple choice tests and open-ended tasks in this type of testing.

Additionally, I frequently manage to arrange diagnostic tests for my students. Because while teaching you must be aware of your student's problems and lacks. This type of testing plays a vital role to identify the learners' challenges and you may tackle them immediately after having analyzed them. In most cases, I organize diagnostic tests after the whole set of lessons or units. They may appear as multiple choice questions and short-answer questions.

As I have some contributions to the private education -- I run my own language center and there I often assemble mock tests for IELTS candidates. Obviously, I maintain proficiency tests in this field. Proficiency tests assist us to measure the level of the language that a learner possesses.

Particularly, I hand in ready-made materials for this kind of testing, obtaining them from formal, authorized institutions (British Council, Cambridge ESOL Exam Preparation Centers).

In terms of formal assessment, my two cents go for organizing daily or weekly tasks in order to explore the learners' casual competences. A scientific approach detects formative assessment as an ongoing process which helps students to identify their strengths and weaknesses.

According to Brookhart (2007) formative assessment bestows information about learning procedure that educators are able to utilize for instructional decisions and learners can manipulate in enhancing their performance.

As an English language teacher I arrange formative assessments on a daily basis. I use quizzes, mini presentations, monologues, internal and external polls, multiple choice questions. They are short, but precise, easy to regulate and implement. Actually, they are meaningful to assess and evaluate the learner. In my opinion, the formative assessment should be reliable, valid and practical. Even though it may be difficult to present authentic materials or tasks, the educator has to establish them in advance and think about their perception and comprehension.

Conclusion

In conclusion, aforementioned tests have become productive in arranging, measuring and analyzing learners' groups, needs, levels, strengths, weaknesses and challenges, additionally, they show a great impact on listening and interactive skills which are ultimate bases for boosting pragmatic competences.

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